

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership in Juhel Pharmaceutical Company in Enugu State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership in Juhel Pharmaceutical Company in Enugu State. The objectives of the study were to: examine the relationship between self-awareness and intellectual stimulation measured by subordinates' perception of leaders; and the relationship between relationship management and idealized influence. A descriptive survey was adopted. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the data. To confirm the significance of the correlation between variables, Pearson correlation analysis was performed. The study revealed that self-awareness had a positive relationship with the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical firms in the Enugu state and that relationship management had a positive relationship with idealized influence. Conclusively, to be effective, leaders must have a solid understanding of how their emotions and actions affect the people around them. It was recommended that the pharmaceutical company should improve its self-awareness strategy in order to improve employees' dedication which will enable intellectual stimulation on the performance of employees, while efficiently delivering outstanding results embark on relationship management and idealized influence.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence; Transformational Leadership; Juhel Pharmaceutical Company

Introduction

The present-day employee expects a safe working environment where he/she can freely voice their opinions and that is where the role of emotionally intelligent leaders becomes crucial. Leaders play an important part in cultivating their team's emotional dynamics. When leaders model the behavior, they want their teams to exhibit, they see their teams develop the same traits. Emotional intelligence was first coined in 1990 by researchers John Mayer and Peter Salovey but was later popularized by psychologist Daniel Goleman. Emotional Intelligence is one's ability to understand and manage their emotions and others' emotions in any situation. It trains leaders to be empathetic. Even before somebody begins to lead others, leadership demands leading oneself emotionally, being aware, and being in command of one's own emotions. The real challenge lies within. One needs to be able to empathize with others and forge relationships that are entrenched in minds and hearts. Emotional Intelligence is the deciding factor in one's success as a leader (Singh, 2022). Irrespective of their cadre in the organization,

all leaders must harness their emotional intelligence skills to not just empower their teams, but the entire organization as a whole. It includes self-awareness, self-management, social skills, and relationship management which are the "sine qua non" of leadership (Goleman, 1998a)

Cooper (2019) defines emotional intelligence as "the ability to sense, understand, and effectively apply the power and acumen of emotions as a source of human energy, information, connection, and influence." While Cherry (2022) asserts that Emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to perceive, control, and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be learned and strengthened, while others claim it's an inborn characteristic. Research shows it is a useful tool for navigating work life, relationships, education, and mental and physical well-being. The ability to express and control emotions is essential, but so is the ability to understand, interpret, and respond to the emotions of others. Imagine a world in which you could not understand when a friend was feeling sad or when a co-worker was angry. Psychologists refer to this ability as emotional intelligence.

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Emotions play a significant role in decision-making, trust-building, employee engagement, and conflict management. When it comes to laying the foundations of a human-centric workforce, the role of Emotional Intelligence is pivotal. Emotionally Intelligent Leaders are committed to improving workplace productivity, team performance, and morale. Emotional Intelligence determines how leaders interact with their teams. Those with high emotional intelligence usually do better in their interpersonal skills, thereby boosting employee morale.

Statement of the problem

Leaders set the tone of their organization. If they lack emotional intelligence, it could have more far-reaching consequences, resulting in lower employee engagement and a higher turnover rate. While leaders might excel at their job technically, if they can't effectively communicate with their team or collaborate with others, those technical skills will get overlooked. A lack of emotional intelligence might inhibit a leader's ability to effectively collaborate and communicate with others. When a leader is not able to manage their emotions, employees might be less eager to share their ideas and are less likely to reach their full potential. With the foregoing, it is worthwhile to examine the effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership in Juhel pharmaceutical companies in the Enugu state.

Objectives of Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership in Juhel Nigeria Ltd, Enugu state. The specific objectives were to;

- I. To ascertain the relationship between self-awareness and intellectual stimulation of employees of Juhel Nigeria Ltd, Enugu state
- II. To evaluate the relationship between relationship management and the idealized influence of employees of Juhel Nigeria Ltd, Enugu state.

Statement of Hypotheses

- I. Self-awareness has no relationship with the intellectual stimulation of employees of Juhel Nigeria Ltd, Enugu state;
- II. Relationship management does not have a significant relationship with idealized employees of Juhel Nigeria Ltd, Enugu state.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Emotions

Emotions constitute the highest form of the sensory relationship between humans and the objects and facts of reality; this relationship is characterized by relative stability, generality, and correlation between needs and values which have been developed throughout an individual's personal development. The formation of stable emotional relationships is the most important presupposition of personality development. It constitutes the main aim and ultimate result of the individual's learning ability. The conscious knowledge of motives, models, and behavioral stipulations alone is not enough to guide the individual's existence within society. On the contrary, only when the individual becomes possessed of stable emotions is this knowledge shaped and formed into behavior. Every aspect of human activity is accompanied by a variety of emotions. The importance of emotional management has led to the designation and study of emotional intelligence and its abilities, especially in organizational settings.

Intelligence

Intelligence has been defined in many ways: higher-level abilities (such as abstract reasoning, mental representation, problem-solving, and decision-making), the ability to learn, emotional knowledge, creativity, and adaptation to meet the demands of the environment effectively. Some researchers argue that intelligence is a general ability, whereas others make the assertion that intelligence comprises specific skills and talents. Psychologists contend that intelligence is genetic or inherited, and others claim that it is largely influenced by the surrounding environment. Sternberg (1997) defines intelligence as "the mental abilities necessary for adaptation to, as well as shaping and selection of, any environmental context.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence is the “ability to monitor one’s own and other people’s emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately, and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior” (Salovey and Mayer, 1990). Emotional intelligence also refers to the ability to know when and how to express emotion as well as being able to control it. Although there is no universal definition for emotional intelligence, however, Goleman (2005) posits that emotional intelligence is a skill that anyone who owns it, tries to control his life with self-awareness and improve it with self-management, and perceives its effects through sympathy or by managing the relations he tries to improve his or others’ moral. Mayer, Salovi, and Caruso, (2007) claim that emotional intelligence is the ability to cognition, evaluation, and expression of emotions, and the ability to control emotions. In yet another definition, Antonakis and Ashkanasy (2009) argue that emotional intelligence includes innate factors (self-awareness, self-control, feeling independence) and external factors (relationship, ease in sympathy, amenability). Yet another definition by Sternberg (1997) asserts that Emotional Intelligence is an indication of how an individual perceives, understands, and regulates emotions. Also, Emotions are brief, organized sets of responses (including physiological changes, expressive behaviors, action tendencies, and subjective experiences) that optimize how individuals address the challenges and exploit the opportunities that arise in the events that they encounter (Levenson 1994). The four key components of emotional Intelligence are (i) self-awareness, (ii) self-management, (iii) social awareness, and (iv) relationship management (Charlotte; 2020).

Components of Emotional Intelligence

Goleman (1995) who popularized emotional intelligence identifies five emotional domains;

- I. **Self-awareness:** which is defined as thinking and concentrating attention on personal experiences and in other words mindfulness, self-awareness is the first part of emotional intelligence. It means to have a deep perception of emotions, power, weak points, needs, and self- motivations. People who have strong self-awareness are honest with themselves and with others (Bello Sabo, 2012).
- II. **Self-regulation:** Socrates thinks that the feeling of composure as the ability to stand against emotional storms of destiny is good quality. We do have to avoid bad feelings to feel the consent although we should not let bad uncontrolled feelings replace all our good spiritual moods (Coleman, 2004).
- III. **Motivations:** Coleman asserts that those who are highly motivated overcome disappointments. An individual, who likes himself because of his work will trust the organization that provides this job for him.
- IV. **Empathy:** Empathy refers to how tuned to the emotions of others a person is. Someone with high EI can accurately identify which emotions another person is feeling and can tell the difference between genuine and false emotions. A person may do this by noticing certain facial expressions or changes in another person’s voice or body language. This feeling stands for self-awareness the higher our self-awareness, the better we can understand the feelings of others. In all relationships, the need to pay attention to others is the ability to feel empathy for them. this ability [the ability to recognize others’ feelings has a role in all stages of life including management, falling in love, and being a father or mother (Coleman,2004)
- V. **Social skills:** more social skills result in a more friendly relationship. Usually, individuals with social skills have many friends, and can easily find common ground with others to build a relationship together.
- VI. **Relationship Management:** Relationship Management (RM) is a relatively new concept; a general definition hence understands RM as strategy, programs, and technology to effectively manage how firms relate to prospective, current, and former employees. When crisis strikes, it is essential to manage many relationships among many people. Employee Relationship is defined as a relationship between the employer or the representative manager and employees, aimed toward maintaining commitment morale, and trust so as to create a productive and secure workplace environment (Bajaj et al., 2013).

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is defined as a leadership approach that causes a change in individuals and social systems. In its ideal form, it creates valuable and positive change in the followers with the end goal of developing followers into leaders. Enacted in its authentic form, transformational leadership enhances the motivation, morale, and performance of followers through a variety of mechanisms. These include connecting the follower's sense of identity and self to the mission and the collective identity of the organization; being a role model for followers that inspires them; challenging followers to take greater ownership of their work, and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of followers, so the leader can align followers with tasks that optimize their performance.

Elements of Transformational Leadership

- I. Individualized Consideration – the degree to which the leader attends to each follower's needs, acts as a mentor or coach to the follower, and listens to the follower's concerns and needs. The leader gives empathy and support, keeps communication open, and places challenges before the followers. This also encompasses the need for respect and celebrates the individual contribution that each follower can make to the team. The followers have a will and aspirations for self-development and have intrinsic motivation for their tasks.
- II. Intellectual Stimulation – the degree to which the leader challenges assumptions, takes risks, and solicits followers' ideas. Leaders with this style stimulate and encourage creativity in their followers. They nurture and develop people who think independently. For such a leader, learning is a value and unexpected situations are seen as opportunities to learn. The followers ask questions, think deeply about things and figure out better ways to execute their tasks. Through intellectual stimulation, transformational leaders encourage followers to question their own beliefs, assumptions, and values, and, when appropriate, those of the leader, which may be outdated or inappropriate for solving current problems (Bass and Avolio, 2004; Elkins and Keller, 2013; Sundi, 2013). Intellectual stimulation is used by leaders to develop employee capabilities of exploring and capturing opportunities to develop performance.
- III. Inspirational Motivation – the degree to which the leader articulates a vision that is appealing and inspiring to followers. Leaders with inspirational motivation challenge followers with high standards, communicate optimism about future goals and provide meaning for the task at hand. The visionary aspects of leadership are supported by communication skills that make the vision understandable, precise, powerful, and engaging.
- IV. Idealized Influence: Idealized influence is the degree to which a leader is perceived as a role model who is confident and can impact employees (Gomes, 2014). It provides a role model for highly ethical behavior, instills pride, and gains respect and trust. At first Idealized influence, can develop employee performance by communicating collective purposes and values, demonstrating confidence and determination, and acting as a charismatic role model (Yue et.al.,2019).

Importance of Emotional Intelligence

In practical terms, being aware that emotions can drive our behavior and impact people (positively and negatively), and learning how to manage those emotions – both our own and others. Managing emotions is especially important in situations when we are under pressure like in;

- I. Giving and receiving feedback
- II. Meeting tight deadlines
- III. Dealing with challenging relationships
- IV. Not having enough resources
- V. Navigating change
- VI. Working through setbacks and failure

It's a scientific fact that emotions precede thought. When emotions run high, they change the way our brains function...diminishing our cognitive abilities, decision-making powers, and even interpersonal skills. Understanding and managing our emotions (and the emotions of others) helps us to be more successful in both our personal and professional lives.

At a personal level, emotional intelligence helps us;

- I. Have uncomfortable conversations without hurting feelings
- II. Manage our emotions when stressed or feeling overwhelmed
- III. Improve relationships with the people we care about

At work, emotional intelligence can help us;

- I. Resolve conflicts
- II. Coach and motivate others
- III. Create a culture of collaboration
- IV. Build psychological safety within teams
- V. Applied to meet goals and targets, as well as create a happier and healthier working culture

Academics and practitioners alike are agreed that the intelligence of human beings and its implications for the organization should be from both cognitive as well as emotional perspectives. They say that as compared to cognitive intelligence, it is emotional intelligence that has greater relevance to organizational success.

Theoretical Framework

Triarchic Theory of Intelligence

The Triarchic Theory of Intelligence was proposed by Robert Sternberg in 1985. The theory is based on the definition of intelligence as the ability to achieve success based on one's personal standards and one's socio-cultural context. According to the triarchic theory, intelligence has three aspects: analytical, creative, and practical (Sternberg, 1985).

- I. **Analytical intelligence** also referred to as componential intelligence, refers to intelligence that is applied to analyze or evaluate problems and arrive at solutions.
- II. **Creative intelligence** is the ability to go beyond what is given to create novel and interesting ideas. This type of intelligence involves imagination, innovation and problem-solving.
- III. **Practical intelligence** is the ability that individuals use to solve problems faced in daily life when a person finds the best fit between themselves and the demands of the environment. Adapting to the demands environment involves either utilizing knowledge gained from experience to purposefully change oneself to suit the environment (adaptation), changing the environment to suit oneself (shaping), or finding a new environment in which to work (selection).

Emotional intelligence has turned out to be progressively mainstream as a measure for distinguishing individuals who are successful in life, and as an instrument for reaching this success. The idea of emotional intelligence clarifies why two individuals of a similar IQ can achieve inconceivably extraordinarily different levels of accomplishment in life (Goleman, 1998) as individuals are in some cases successful not due to their knowledge, but rather because of their capacity to interact with individuals socially and emotionally by utilizing charming temperament in their exchanges (St.Clair, 2004).

Empirical Review

Anton and Jacoba (2005), research on Leader emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, trust, and team commitment: testing a model within a team context in South Africa. The model was tested using structural equation modeling (SEM); an acceptable level of model fit was found. Significant positive relationships were further found among all the constructs. Such an integrated model has not been tested in a team context before and the positive findings, therefore, add to existing teamwork literature.

Ismail et al. (2009) carried out a study to measure the effect of transformational leadership characteristics and empowerment on service quality by using 110 usable questionnaires collected from staff employed in a city-based local authority in Sarawak, Malaysia. The results from a stepwise regression analysis showed that the relationship between empowerment and selected transformational leadership characteristics such as intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration is positively and significantly correlated with service quality. Further, intellectual stimulation was found to be not significantly correlated with service quality which indicates that intellectual stimulation does not affect the performance of an employee in the city-based local authority.

Leonard, George, Peter, and Michael (2016), research on Effect of Intellectual Stimulation and Individualized Consideration on Staff Performance in State Owned Enterprises in Kenya. The study used factor analysis to reduce data, correlation analysis to establish the relationship between staff performance and intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration, chi-square test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and a multiple linear regression model to test the hypotheses. The study found that intellectual stimulation was positively and significantly related with staff performance. Individualized consideration was strongly correlated with staff performance and significantly predicted staff performance.

Mary, Damary, and Teresia (2017), research on the Influence of Intellectual Stimulation Leadership Behaviour on Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya. A correlational research design was employed to investigate the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Pearson's correlation, multiple regression, and chi-square techniques were used to analyze the data. The results showed that intellectual stimulation leadership behavior and Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya had a strong positive and significant correlation.

Israel, Marisa, and Susana (2017), research on Leadership Intellectual Stimulation and Team Learning: the Mediating Role of Team Positive effect. Using a cross-sectional sample of 562 employees, nested within 130 teams from 44 small- and medium-sized organizations, we implemented a Structural Equation Model analysis at the team level. Results provide evidence of the strong relationship that intellectual stimulation has on team learning and team positive affect, as well as the potential of positive affect for stimulating team learning. Team positive effect serves as a partial mediator between intellectual stimulation and team learning, contributing to explaining significant additional variance. Leadership intellectual stimulation is a relevant team social resource that provides support for team learning. Also, positive affect contributes significantly to improving learning among teams.

Rana and Ajmal (2012), researched the Transformational Leadership Style as Predictor of Decision-Making Styles: Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence in Pakistan. Regression analysis is utilized to study the relationship between transformational leadership style and decision-making styles and step-wise regression analysis is used to study moderating effect of emotional intelligence. The study found that transformational leadership style strongly predicts rational and dependent decision-making styles and weakly predicts intuitive and spontaneous decision-making styles while no association was found with avoidant decision-making styles. The present research also found that emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between transformational leadership styles and decision-making styles.

Shahram (2014) researched the Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership in Sports Managers in Iran. The method of the study was a correlation. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics including mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum scores, Pearson correlation formula, independent t-test, and multiple regression analysis. The results revealed significant positive correlations, both simple and multiple, between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership style in the sports managers in Alborz province.

Juma and Ndisya (2016) investigated the Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance. A Case Study of Safaricom Limited. Strategic. The influence of intellectual stimulation on employee performance was examined using five measures namely: Employee's opportunity to work in a way they think best; consent to determine their own pace for change; consent to make a judgment in unraveling a problem; employee's receipt of assistance to reconsider ideas that had never been looked into; and employees' challenge to deliberate on old problems in new ways.

Liberty and Kida (2017) examined the effect of emotional intelligence on employees' performance with the aim of understanding the influence of emotional intelligence of employees on their performance in the organization. The variables studied were emotional intelligence on organizational employee performance. Six organizations from mixed industries in operation in Maiduguri Borno State were studied. Questionnaires were administered on the 121 samples which were determined purposely. A Chi-Square (X²) was used to test the hypotheses formulated. It was found that the use of emotional intelligence was a more potent drive to any accomplishment than monetary rewards.

Otienoa, Teresia, and Damary (2019), studied the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The objective of the study was to investigate the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. A correlational research design was conducted with the purpose of determining the strength of the relationship between parameters of idealized influence and employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The findings showed that employee engagement has a statistically significant relationship with charisma, ethical leadership, and teamwork. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that employee motivation positively and significantly moderates the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was utilized for the study. Descriptive research is concerned with the description of data and characteristics about a population. The goal is the acquisition of factual, accurate and systematic data and to describe the data and characteristics about what is being studied. It is also useful because of the relatively large population from which the information was collected. This study adopts a primary source of data. This was gotten from the respondents by the use of structured questionnaire. Questionnaire was structured in line with the variables of the study already stated in the hypotheses. The area of the study is located at Enugu metropolis with reference to Juhel pharmaceutical company. The population of study comprised of all the employees of Juhel pharmaceutical company, Enugu. Data for this study were collected from subordinates (who rated their supervisors' EI and the

components of TFL behavior) working at different section of the organizations. The total population of the subordinate employees of the organizations are two thousand, one hundred and forty-seven (2140). The instrument for data collection utilized for the study was structured questionnaire. The Likert-type scale or category was adopted for analysis, namely: strongly agree; (SA); Agree (A); Undecided (UD); Disagree (DA); and Strongly Disagree (SD). Each level is assigned a number ranging from 5 (SA) to 1 (SD). Also used were Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Some Extent (SE), Little Extent (LE), and Very Little Extent (VLE). Each level is assigned a number ranging from 5 (VGE) to 1 (VLE). The completed questionnaire forms were collected, coded and subsequently analyzed. Tables, percentages, frequencies and mean were used as the analytical tools; while t-test of population proportion was used to test the formulated hypotheses at alpha level set at 0.05.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data Presentation

Data Analyses

Table 1: Means, Standard Deviations, Reliabilities, and Correlations among Variables

Variable	Mean	SD	B	1	2	3
1. EI	4.93	1.01	.97	1		
2. IS	2.51	0.72	.84	0.68**	1	
3. II	2.62	0.71	.80	0.67**	.80**	1

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); N = 266; EQI = emotional Intelligence index; II = idealized influence; IM = inspirational motivation; IS = intellectual stimulation; and IC = individualized consideration.

Examination of Table 1 shows that there were significant correlations between EI and the components of TL. EI was found to relate significantly with the intellectual stimulation ($r = 0.62, p < 0.01$) (leaders stimulate their followers' effort to be innovative and creative) and idealized influence ($r = 0.65, p < 0.01$), (leaders are admired, respected, and trusted), inspirational motivation ($r = 0.67, p < 0.01$), (leaders provide challenge and a mutual understanding of objectives), It indicates that all two hypotheses were supported by the results.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 2: Summary of Regression Analysis regarding EQI and Components of TFL

Components of TL (Explained variables)	EI (Predictors)				
	Coefficient (B)	S.E (B)	Value of t-statistic	Value of R ²	Value of F-statistics (ANOVA)
1. EI	0.47	0.044	10.85**	.43	114.08**
2. IS	0.48	0.045	11.54**	.45	130.93**
3. II	0.49	0.0446	9.98**	.39	99.45**

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); N = 266; EI = emotional intelligence index; ; IS = intellectual stimulation; II = idealized influence

Table 2 indicates that about 42%, 44%, 38%, and 39% of the variance in II and, IS was explained by EI respectively. It is, thus, suggested that EI exclusively can be the significant predictor in explaining the components of transformational leaders (TL.)

Discussion of Findings

Organizations that are able to create commitment among their employees realize that commitment is ultimately personal. It requires consistency in action at the same time as recognizing the need for flexibility and requires making decisions about what employees are prepared and not prepared to do. However, employees themselves also have to be willing to make the effort needed to improve their skills to help them better meet organizational goals. (Vambe and Okafor, 2015). This was supported by the result of hypothesis one, f-calculated {4248.823} is greater that the f-tabulated {2.3719}, that is, $f_{cal} > f_{tab}$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept Alternative hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the social awareness has effect on intellectual stimulation on performance of employees of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.

From the result, f -calculated {761.285} is greater than the f -tabulated {2.3719}, that is, f -Cal > f -tab. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept Alternative hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that relationship management does not have effect idealized influence of performance of employees of pharmaceutical companies in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The findings at the end of the study include the following:

- I. Self-awareness had a significant positive relationship with intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu state.
- II. Relationship management had a significant positive relationship with idealized influence of employees of pharmaceutical companies in Enugu state.

Conclusion

To be effective, leaders must have a solid understanding of how their emotions and actions affect the people around them. The better a leader relates to and works with others, the more successful he or she will be. Take the time to work on self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Working on these areas will help you excel in the future!

Recommendations

- I. The Pharmaceutical company should improve their self-awareness strategy in order to improve employees' dedication that will enable intellectual stimulation on performance of employees, while efficiently deliver outstanding results.
- II. pharmaceutical companies in South East, Nigeria should embark on relationship management and idealized influence to help achieve results in high-priority areas, train directors and administrators on fundamentals of performance management systems and the measurement of key performance indicators.

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